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Computational tools to analyse protein variant effects

List of links to tools and references

- **ClinVar**

ClinVar is a freely accessible, public database hosted by the National Center for Biotechnology Information (NCBI), a part of the National Institutes of Health (NIH) in the United States. It is designed to provide information about the relationships between human variations and phenotypes, with the phenotypes being observable traits. ClinVar aggregates data about genetic mutations, including single nucleotide variants, insertions/deletions, and larger structural changes, along with their observed health impacts.

The database serves as a valuable resource for clinicians, researchers, and patients by offering an authoritative and comprehensive repository of clinically relevant genetic variations. Each entry in ClinVar includes detailed information about the variant, such as the types of mutation, the gene affected, and its relationship to specific diseases or conditions. These entries are supported by evidence from the literature, expert panel evaluations, and laboratory test results, providing a basis for understanding the potential clinical significance of genetic variants.

Link: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/clinvar/>

Tool: <https://simple-clinvar.broadinstitute.org/>

- **gnomAD**

the Genome Aggregation Database (gnomAD) is a large-scale, public resource that aggregates and harmonizes exome and genome sequencing data from a diverse set of individuals to aid in the understanding of human genetic variation. Hosted by the Broad Institute, gnomAD compiles data from numerous studies and projects, including both from healthy individuals those with specific diseases, covering various populations worldwide. This extensive database includes information on millions of variants, providing insights into the frequency of these variants across different populations.

gnomAD is invaluable for researchers and clinicians in the fields of genetics and genomics, offering a comprehensive reference for identifying the significance of genetic variants. By cataloguing variations in the human genome, gnomAD helps distinguish between common, benign variants and those that are potentially pathogenic or associated with disease, its rich dataset supports the development of genetic diagnostics, the discovery of new disease-associated genes, and the refinement of genetic testing guidelines.

Tool: <https://gnomad.broadinstitute.org/>

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- **EVE**

The EVE method leverages deep learning to predict the pathogenicity of human missense variants by analysing the distribution of sequence variation across species. Using a variational autoencoder (VAE), EVE captures the constraints of natural sequences throughout evolution, including the interdependencies between amino acid positions. This model is trained on a vast dataset of about 250 million protein sequences from UniRef, focusing on multiple sequence alignments for each human protein of interest. After training, EVE calculates an 'evolutionary index' for each amino acid variant compared to the wild type by sampling from the VAE's learned distribution.

This approach surpasses previous methods in accuracy and stability, using a two-step process to determine pathogenicity. Initially, it avoids traditional supervisor learning techniques, instead applying a mixture of Gaussian models to the evolutionary indices of all variants to generate a continuous pathogenicity score (EVE score) ranging from 0 (benign) to 1 (pathogenic). Variants are categorized into benign, uncertain, or pathogenic based on the predictive entropy of this model, indicating a novel and sophisticated method for assessing variant pathogenicity without direct supervision.

Tool: <https://evemodel.org/>

Article: <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41586-021-04043-8>

- **ESM-Variants**

The ESM1b approach, leveraging advancements in deep learning, represents a significant shift in variant effect prediction (VEP) methodologies within human genetics. Unlike traditional methods that often require explicit homology or are dependent on labelled data distinguishing pathogenic from benign variants, ESM1b employs protein language models derived from natural language processing techniques. This method involves deep neural networks trained on an extensive dataset of protein sequences, such as the ~250 million sequences in UniProt to model the evolutionary landscape of protein structures and functions.

The distinction of ESM1b lies in its capacity to estimate the likelihood of any amino acid sequence and its impact on protein functionality without needing direct comparisons to known protein families or structures. This model implicitly learns a broad range of protein features, including secondary structure, interaction sites, and post-translational modifications, directly from sequence data. With 650 million parameters, ESM1b is among the largest protein language models available, capable of predicting gene variants with high accuracy, as evidenced by its correlation with experimental results from deep mutational scans (DMS) without further training.

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This approach starkly contrasts with EVE, which relies on unsupervised learning from multiple sequence alignments (MSA) to predict the pathogenicity of variants. While EVE represents a breakthrough in leveraging evolutionary data without labelled datasets, its predictions are confined to well-aligned proteins and residues, and it may struggle to differentiate the effects of variants on alternative protein isoforms. In comparison, ESM1b model does not hinge on homology or alignment quality, providing a more flexible and comprehensive tool for assessing the potential impacts of genetic variants across the entire protein sequence space.

Link: <https://github.com/facebookresearch/esm?tab=readme-ov-file>

Tool: <https://huggingface.co/ntranoslab>

Article: <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41588-023-01465-0>

- **AlphaMissense**

AlphaMissense is an innovative tool designed to bridge the gap in variant interpretation by predicting the pathogenicity of missense variants, which alter amino acid sequences in proteins and can disrupt function, affection organismal fitness. It addresses the challenge in human genetics where over 4 million observed missense variants exist, but only 2% have been clinically categorized, leveraging the majority with uncertain significance. This limitation hampers the diagnosis or rare disease and the development of targeted treatments.

Leveraging unsupervised protein language modelling and structural insights from AlphaFold, AlphaMissense fine-tunes predictions using population frequency data, this circumventing biases from human-curated annotations. It sets a new standard in missense pathogenicity predictions, offering a database of predictions for all possible single amino acid substitutions in the human proteome. With this toll, 32% of missense variants are classified as likely pathogenic and 57% as likely benign with high precision, significantly enhancing our understanding and prediction accuracy for most human missense variants.

AlphaMissense serves as a valuable resource for molecular biologists, human geneticists, and clinicians by accelerating research, aiding in the design of experiments, quantifying the functional significance of genes, and improving the diagnostic process for rare diseases. It underscores the potential of integrating structural modelling and machine learning to illuminate the molecular impacts of genetic variants, aiding in the discovery of disease-causing genes and advancing the field of genetic diagnostics.

Link: <https://github.com/google-deepmind/alphamissense>

Tool: <https://alphamissense.hegelab.org/>

Article: <https://www.science.org/doi/10.1126/science.adg7492>

